

EUROPEAN TRANSPORT CONFERENCE
2021

COVID-19 impact on light electric mobility: Analysis of electro-mobility trends and corresponding guidelines for planning authorities and service providers

Papí Ferrando, José Francisco
Kühl, Friederike Lena
Etelätär Innovation

Cosso, Elena
Repetto, Cino
TBridge

Smart mobility planning within the context of smart cities may lead to a mobility future likely to differ in significant ways from today's systems. Light Electric Vehicles (EL-Vs), being smaller and lighter than passenger cars, account for a significant percentage of urban trips. This is due to a significantly reduced trip duration, reduced fuel consumption and reduced search traffic congestion in city centres.

In order to explore the possible impact of these vehicles on existing European urban transportation networks, in 2017 the ELVITEN¹ project was funded by the European Commission. The vision of ELVITEN is to craft replicable usage schemes, consisting of support services, Information and Communications Technology (ICT) tools and policies, to boost the usage (whether through private ownership or sharing models) of individual and professional users of electrified L-category vehicles (bicycles, scooters, tricycles and quadricycles). Its aim is to familiarise users with the vehicles and facilitate the access to and usage of EL-Vs instead of Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles for their private transport and for light urban deliveries as well as to generate detailed guidelines and business models for service providers, planning authorities and manufacturers to make EL-Vs more attractive and more integrated in the transport infrastructure and electricity networks.

The demonstrations, including 193 EL-Vs and over 600 users, started in April 2019 and were completed on 30th June 2020. In spring 2020, when the COVID-19 pandemic struck Europe, the pilot demonstrations in Berlin (Germany), Trikala (Greece), Málaga (Spain), and Genoa, Roma and Bari (Italy) turned into a privileged observatory to understand the effects of the pandemic on the users' behaviour and new mobility needs of European citizens. Thanks to the analysis of the data collected in the pilot cities, it was possible to obtain useful indications on how the EL-Vs and relevant services and tools responded to users' needs and subsequently, the necessary adaptations for existing transportation infrastructures could be derived from these COVID-19 implications.

In this paper the analysis of mobility trends carried out comparing data from the pre-COVID period with those collected during the pandemic period as well as the

EUROPEAN TRANSPORT CONFERENCE 2021

guidelines addressed to planning authorities and EL-Vs mobility service providers are reported and further discussed. During the project the users' behaviour and opinions were recorded by means of data collection from multiple sources, including questionnaires, booking information, monitoring of vehicle activity, and charging behaviour. The results take into account the experience acquired within the ELVITEN project, reviewed and integrated in the light of the evidence, trends and market drivers observed during the pandemic period.

The needs and habits of users have been changed profoundly by the lockdowns during the pandemic and will have repercussions for the years to come. Our belief is that these lessons learned can help planning authorities and service providers to propose new mobility models and to adapt the existing business models for EL-V sharing, rental, parking, safety of health and charge services to the new context, which will affect urban transport systems at least in the short and medium term.

1. Introduction

Within only a few weeks after the COVID-19 virus reached Europe in the spring of 2020, the sanitary situation across the continent turned into a state of emergency in large parts of the European Union. Some countries simply discouraged citizens to leave their homes or go to work unless necessary and issued curfews, while others decreed the total halt of life outside home with strict lockdowns, which prevented citizens to leave their home except to run essential errands. Social gatherings were prohibited and only critical workers (among others medical personnel, employees of supermarkets or agricultural businesses) commuted to and from their place of work. Those who did travel refrained in large parts from using shared services or public transport due to the increased risk of infection in closed spaces. Individual, sustainable, powerful and convenient mobility became more attractive than ever before. The significant impact on the European users' behaviour, their new mobility needs as well as their choices' impact on the electro-mobility sector stand in the spotlight of this study.

The data analysis conducted within the ELVITEN research project as well as additional data collected in the pilot cities or this project helped to obtain useful indications on how the EL-Vs complemented other modes of transport during the pandemic (Papí Ferrando, García Aletta, & Díaz-Guardamino García, 2020). The project's data is not only insightful since it renders user behaviour prior, during and after the lockdowns comparable but it also represents the largest study on EL-V travelling behaviour ever conducted.

2. Changes in mobility behaviour during COVID-19 measures

During the final months of the ELVITEN project, the COVID-19 virus arrived in European cities with full force and changed the public perspective and the mobility

EUROPEAN TRANSPORT CONFERENCE 2021

markets behaviour across the world. After the initial crisis, millions of people had been confined inside their homes without being able to go out with the exception to carry out basic activities. Countries who chose a softer approach still discouraged any kind of travel or social gatherings and tried to prevent further spreading of the disease through curfews, preventing them from leaving their home during certain times of the day. Only the so-called essential workers, persons who are vital to the upkeep of the most basic services were exempt, including for example medical personnel, emergency responders or supermarket workers. This situation changed the electromobility market status-quo, as proven by several studies analysing e-mobility demand variation during the COVID-19 crisis (Van Audenhove, Rominger, Pourbaix, & Dommergues, 2020). At the beginning of the COVID pandemic, during the first week of an acute crisis and before the mandatory lockdown, available data reported an exponential increase in the demand of electric bicycle sharing services.

For instance, Billy Bike², in Brussels (Chini, 2020) has doubled its demand. In New York, provider City Bike increased its usage rate by 67% (Hazan, Marteau, & Fassnot, 2020). Providing individual transport, easy disinfecting and open-to-the-air vehicles, EL-V sharing services have become more attractive to the public. Also, hesitation to use public transport due to social distancing recommendations from the authorities in the immediate post lockdown period is steadily redirecting demand from these services to EL-Vs.

Public transportation planning and usage is changing drastically due to the general population's rising fear and risk to catch the virus. Furthermore, restrictions have been implemented to ensure public safety. Reducing public transport capacity, mandatory use of facial masks or respecting social distancing in every public transport mode are some of these measures. They mean increased inconvenience for the user, who is forced to look for new alternatives for daily commuting or usual transport. Alternatives such as vehicle sharing services reduce exposure to the virus while being less restrictive and more convenient. These characteristics make the user more willing to use these services.

When this emergency phase will be over it will be important to adapt local public transport to the new needs of citizens and to think about integrated solutions between public transports and EL-Vs. Figure 1 below visualises the demand for public transport services in Madrid, Spain during the COVID-19 crisis:

Figure 1: Demand of public transport services during COVID-19 crisis in Madrid (1 March – 1 May 2020)

Also, after the COVID-19 crisis, the global EL-V market is forecasted to grow, especially in developing countries such as India, where 30 to 40 percent of electric scooters are expected to be electric in the next 7 or 8 years (Priya, 2020). In the first affected country by COVID-19, China, the charging stations sector has grown its new installed infrastructure by 513,000 public and 714,000 privately-owned charging stations, an increase of 43.8 percent compared to 2019. Not only in developing countries but also in developed ones, EL-Vs are forecasted to become a main actor in mobility, increasing their share from 5-10% to 30% (Heineke, Kloss, & Scurtu, 2019). EL-V markets are becoming more attractive for both private and public transport; their business attractiveness has therefore increased in comparison with the pre-COVID-19 context. Figure 2 shows the public e-bike sharing service demand in Madrid, where there was a clear trend emerging:

Figure 2: Public sharing service demand in Madrid during COVID-19 confinement

Furthermore, the demand in the ELVITEN pilots also suffered the effects of confinement and COVID-19. In the Table 1 and Figure 3 below, the numbers of trips during and post confinement shows a clear trend.

Table 1 - ELVITEN project number of trips February – June 2020

City	Average trips/month (start pilot-Feb 2020)	Trips in March 2020	Trips in April 2020	Tips in May 2020	Trips in June 2020
Bari	326	269	10	870	1,628
Berlin	328	277	293	331	136
Genoa	218	260	214	128	224
Malaga	377	578	165	417	320
Rome	571	764	318	834	425
Trikala	511	593	454	980	1,123
Total	2,229	2,741	1,454	3,560	3,856

Figure 3 – ELVITEN project EL-V trip evolution March – May 2020

It is worth noting that leisure trips were more frequent during and after the COVID-19 lockdown than in the rest of the demonstrations. The number of leisure trips increased significantly from mid-April until the end of demonstrations. Work education trips showed a noticeable reduction to 37.68% during the same period (March-April 2020),

from 67.51% from the project start until February 2020. This can be observed comparing Figure 4 and Figure 5 below.

Figure 4 - ELVITEN project trips by purpose pre-COVID-19

Figure 5 - ELVITEN project trips during COVID-19 lockdowns (15 March - 03 May 2020)

3. Impact on electro-mobility sector due to COVID-19 measures

The crisis linked to the COVID-19 emergency is likely to have permanent effects on existing urban mobility systems. This is true both in the medium term, with the need to adapt to the safety requirements defined for the post lockdown phase and subsequent phases, and in the long term, when it will be necessary to verify the real impact of the crisis on the behaviour of citizens, which will be consolidated over time. The data collected in the pilot cities during the demonstrations confirmed the trends that are taking place at European and global level.

The framework outlined is part of a context in which players continue to offer a wide and innovative range of services that meet the needs of citizens. The further development, fine-tuning and the success of many services will depend on their ability to identify and meet society's emerging needs both on the short and on the long term.

Short-term electro-mobility sharing services require a modular approach and easy maintenance as well as sanitary disinfection. Ideally, vehicles should be sanitised automatically inside closed charging or parking facilities after each rental and customers should be required to wear face masks at all times. Furthermore, the use of personal equipment, such as helmets or gloves should be encouraged and the sanitary protocol could be checked, for example by requiring customers to take a picture of themselves wearing a mask before they can unlock the vehicle (Lozzi, Marcucci, Gatta, Pacelli, & Teoh, 2020).

Figure 6 - Disinfection of short-term rental electric scooters

For long-term sharing services, the requirements are different since customers do not exchange vehicles on a daily basis. They could consist in providing larger parking and

EUROPEAN TRANSPORT CONFERENCE 2021

rental facilities, offering a contactless check-in, or integrating the service in a regular sanitation service to disinfect the vehicles.

In order to overcome the challenging environment of COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 mobility markets, the companies need to adapt their business models and sharing approaches for more safety and flexibility.

4. Adapted business models and opportunities

During the pandemic, different European mobility service providers started reinventing themselves to make their services more suitable to customers' needs. For example, Sharengo³, an Italian company founded to allow the sharing of electric cars in cities, promptly developed a new proposal to adapt to the disruption brought to the sector by the coronavirus pandemic and launched MySharengo, which allows the long-term rental of cars. Unlike car sharing, where you take the car and leave it after the trip, with MySharengo you can rent a car for a time ranging from a month to a year. The car will be delivered sanitised and equipped with a kit, which includes the Sharengo Card, with which you can open and close the vehicle, charging cable, user and maintenance manual of the car, disinfectant gel, reflective vest and emergency triangle. (Anonymous, Sharengo Website, s.d.)

As an example of the implementation of mobility as a service, a new way to plan your urban travel by booking all the necessary means of transport from a single platform and paying by subscription or forfait, it can be mentioned Helbiz⁴, an Italian company that launched Helbiz Unlimited, the first subscription in Italy for sustainable mobility that allows you to pay for the rental of scooters and electric bikes in a single solution. (Anonymous, Helbiz Website, s.d.)

The pandemic has also affected the purchasing power of households, so service providers will also face an additional challenge: making their services accessible to a population in economic difficulty. According to industry experts, each household spends around 20% of its assets on transport every year. (Huhtala-Jenks, Head of Ecosystem & Sustainability, MaaS Global) In fact, in the immediate post lock down period, within the automotive market it was observed a collapse in sales, but the first market that registered a surge was that of EL-Vs, supported also by national incentives. (Di Paola Galloni, 2020)

5. Conclusions

During the confinement, demand drastically dropped due to the interdiction for citizens to leave their homes and mandatory telework when applicable. However, once restrictions began to lift, demand increased to surpass the average pre-COVID-19 scenario in more than 800 trips per month. This data supports the hypothesis that users are more interested on EL-V services because of EL-Vs characteristics and the possibility of maintaining social distancing while commuting or undertaking daily trips. This trend will keep increasing services demand once restrictions are completely lifted in each urban area where ELVITEN vehicles are deployed.

Not only the current situation helps the EL-V market grow but also their environmental impact, which is a big social challenge which EL-Vs can contribute to: EL-Vs have lower emissions and their CO₂ emissions are decentralised. These advantages are also coupled with remarkable economic benefits, because an EL-V is cheaper than a motor vehicle and its maintenance and operation costs are also lower. This makes EL-Vs a very promising complement to public transport and private commuting. To sum up, the main COVID-19 effects on EL-Vs markets that are emerging are as follows:

- Increasing demand for EL-V sharing systems.
- EL-Vs allow easy disinfecting in individual transport.
- EL-V market growth, especially in developing countries.
- EL-Vs as a suitable complement to public transport and commuting.

This situation highlights the need for the mobility sector to reinvent itself in some way to adapt to the upcoming challenges arising from COVID-19. Operators, software developers, vehicle manufacturers, public services and public authorities will all have to be creative to find ways to address a wide range of social, technical and commercial problems created or exacerbated by the pandemic.

In sum, the main aspects that service providers must consider are:

- Safety and hygiene: hygiene is perhaps the most significant psychological barrier to the use of shared mobility in this era of COVID-19. In the next future, those who manage to convince users that their vehicles are the safest will have a significant advantage over those who may not have the resources to do so.
- Strategy: shared mobility services will, at least currently, only serve the local population. This is an important change for some operators who were heavily dependent on revenues generated by tourists. Now it might be useful to shift from short-term offers to monthly subscriptions to maintain a low cost per trip for all new regular users.

EUROPEAN TRANSPORT CONFERENCE 2021

- Integration: technological innovations such as platforms for the integration of mobility services, and market innovations such as sharing services (cars, bikes and scooters) can and should contribute to the development of sustainable mobility provision for all citizens.
- Booking convenience: smart e-ticketing coordinated with multimodal offering has not yet been implemented, even if local administrations believe it is a service to be implemented in the future. The most important operational requirements' need are apps for online booking and payment, which would make booking and any shared service much more convenient.

6. Bibliography

- Heineke, K., Kloss, B., & Scurtu, D. (2019). *Micromobility: Industry progress, and a closer look at the case of Munich*. McKinsey Center for Future Mobility.
- Priya, S. (2020, 04 27). *Economic Times India Auto*. Retrieved 06 15, 2020, from India's electric story to continue, to be dominated by light mobility post Covid-19: <https://auto.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/industry/indias-electric-story-to-continue-to-be-dominated-by-light-mobility-post-covid-19/75284206>
- Anonymous. (n.d.). *Helbiz Website*. Retrieved June 15, 2020, from <https://www.helbiz.com/unlimited>: <https://helbiz.com/>
- Anonymous. (2020, May 07). *Lyft Blog*. Retrieved June 15, 2020, from <https://www.lyft.com/blog/posts/lyft-launching-health-safety-program>
- Anonymous. (n.d.). *Sharengo Website*. Retrieved June 15, 2020, from <https://site.sharengo.it/en/>: <https://www.sharengo.com/>
- Chini, M. (2020, 04). Number of electric bike journeys has doubled, says Billy Bike. *The Brussels Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.brusselstimes.com/brussels/108558/number-of-electric-bike-journeys-has-doubled-says-billy-bike/>
- Di Paola Galloni, J.-L. (2020). *Corporate Vice-President Sustainability and External Affairs, Valeo Group*.
- Grea, G. (2020, May 25). *Citytech Live*. Retrieved July 05, 2020, from <https://citytechlive.com/2020/05/25/gabriele-grea-articolo/>
- Hazan, J., Marteau, P., & Fassenot, B. (2020, April 26). *Toutes les conditions sont réunies pour un retour irréversible de la suprématie de la voiture individuelle*, *Le Monde*. Retrieved May 06, 2020, from https://www.lemonde.fr/idees/article/2020/04/26/toutes-les-conditions-sont-reunies-pour-un-retour-irreversible-de-la-suprematie-de-la-voiture-individuelle_6037800_3232.html
- Huhtala-Jenks, K. (Head of Ecosystem & Sustainability, MaaS Global).
- Onorato, L. (2020, May 04). *Covid-19: l'impatto sul futuro della mobilità*, *Deloitte Blog*. Retrieved June 15, 2020, from <https://www2.deloitte.com/it/it/blog/italy/2020/covid-19---futuro-della-mobilita---luigi-onorato.html>
- Van Audenhove, F.-J., Rominger, G., Pourbaix, J., & Dommergues, E. (2020). *The future of mobility post-covid*. Brussels, Belgium: UITP.
- Yuanyuan, L. (2020, March 30). *COVID-19 brings the growth of China's charging station sector to a month-long halt*, *Renewable Energy World*. Retrieved May 06, 2020, from <https://www.renewableenergyworld.com/storage/covid-19-brings-the-growth-of-chinas-charging-station-sector-to-a-month-long-halt/#gref>
- Papí Ferrando, J. F., García Aletta, F. M., & Díaz-Guardamino García, I. (2020). *D5.1 Real mobility needs of EL-Vs's users*. ELVITEN Consortium.
- Lozzi, G., Marcucci, E., Gatta, V., Pacelli, V. R., & Teoh, T. (2020). *COVID-19 and urban mobility: impacts and perspectives*. TRAN Committee, European

EUROPEAN TRANSPORT CONFERENCE 2021

Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies,
Directorate-General for Internal Policies.
(n.d.).

7. Notes

1. <https://www.elviten-project.eu/en/>
2. <https://www.billy.bike/>
3. <http://www.sharengo.eu/>
4. <https://helbiz.com/>